

Child Labour and Long-Term Absence in Japanese Fishing Villages during the 1950s Post-War Recovery

This study examines whether Japanese prefectures with documented child labour in 1950s fishing villages show elevated rates of incomplete compulsory education. Using prefecture-level data from the 2020 National Population Census, this study focuses on adults who did not complete junior high school, relating these outcomes to historical evidence of long-term school absence associated with fisheries-based labour. Based on a systematic review, prefectures were classified into Group A, where absence was primarily linked to labour demands, and Group B, where labour was accompanied by documented trafficking practices. Group-level comparisons show that non-completion was higher than the national average (0.70%) among Group A men (0.89%) and Group B women (1.53%). At the prefectural level, particularly pronounced rates were observed among men in Hiroshima (4.25%) and women in Okinawa (5.66%), consistent with historically documented labour-related educational disruption. The study highlights the relevance of adult literacy and lifelong learning from a life-course perspective.

Keywords: Long-term absence; child labour and education; Japanese fishing villages; Post-war Japan; compulsory education; marginalised communities

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This study uses publicly available data from the Japanese Population Census (MIC, 2020) and contemporaneous surveys cited in the references. No new data were created.

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Introduction

Surveys have shown that some cohorts did not complete compulsory schooling, but the occupational and social contexts of long-term absence have not been systematically connected to later evidence of non-completion in national statistics.

A particularly important context is child labour in fishing villages during the 1950s, despite 1947 reforms (Tomita 1951; Sato 1957). This study asks: to what extent was child labour in fishing communities associated with long-term absence and the non-completion of compulsory education? For clarity, this paper distinguishes between long-term absence as defined in contemporaneous surveys and non-completion as recorded in the National Population Census. This distinction raises the question of how census data can be used to interpret long-term educational patterns associated with post-war child labour.

Post-war reforms extended compulsory schooling to nine years, yet fishing communities struggled to adjust. The need for children to contribute to family income often conflicted with attendance requirements, being associated with persistent long-term absence from junior high school.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) defines child labour as work harmful to children's development, and Convention No. 138 (1973) set the minimum

working age at 15 (ILO et al. 2019, 18). In Japan, the 1947 Constitution and Labour Standards Act likewise prohibited employment under 15, but exceptions for agriculture and fishing created loopholes that sustained child labour (Eguchi 2022, 73). Government reports also addressed exploitative fosterage or indenture, described in the period as *jinshin baibai* ('human sale'), practices that this paper categorises under the English terms child labour and human trafficking.

Japan-based educational historiography, exemplified by Eguchi (2022), has played a crucial role in bringing into view the historically marginalised experiences of non-enrolment and long-term absence that accompanied the post-war expansion of compulsory education. However, these accounts have necessarily relied on documentary reconstruction and case-based narratives, leaving unresolved how such exclusions were distributed and persisted at the population level under formally universal educational institutions. By introducing census-based statistical evidence into this historiographical terrain, this study responds to a theoretical limitation of existing work: the absence of a population-level lens through which the uneven reach of institutional universality can be assessed. This study draws on Basu's (1999) framework, which conceptualises child labour as household labour demand operating within specific institutional arrangements.

This study focuses on the long-term correspondence between labour-related

educational disruption documented in fishing villages during the 1950s and patterns of incomplete compulsory education observed in the 2020 Population Census. Other themes addressed in the manuscript, including child trafficking, adult literacy, and lifelong learning, are examined insofar as they contextualise or follow from this central analytical focus.

Historical context of compulsory education and long-term absence in post-war Japan

Following the 1947 education reforms, Japan formally extended compulsory schooling to nine years, encompassing both elementary and junior high education. Enrolment in junior high school expanded rapidly during the late 1940s and 1950s, and continuous attendance increasingly became the normative expectation for children up to the age of fifteen. While long-term absenteeism was recognised as a broader social issue in post-war Japan, the evidence reviewed here suggests that in fishing villages absenteeism was not merely episodic but structurally embedded in household labour arrangements, leading to distinctive patterns of junior high school non-completion.

Fishing villages occupied a distinctive position within this broader educational transition. Unlike urban or industrial settings, many fishing communities were

characterised by household-based production, strong reliance on family labour, and pronounced seasonal labour peaks. Children were often incorporated into work from an early age through practices of skill transmission and apprenticeship that were embedded in local labour regimes. In this respect, practices of skill transmission and apprenticeship in fishing villages can be understood as historically specific manifestations of household labour demand, rather than as separate or opposing logics. Children's incorporation into work combined immediate labour needs with expectations of occupational continuity, thereby intensifying tensions with the institutional requirements of compulsory schooling. These structural features sustained conflicts with junior high school attendance, even after compulsory education had been formally established.

In particular, Okinawa followed a distinct administrative trajectory under U.S. occupation until 1972, during which educational governance differed from that of mainland Japan. In this study, Okinawa is therefore not treated as directly equivalent to other prefectures, but as a conditionally comparable case that illustrates how similar labour practices intersected with different institutional arrangements.

Methods

Mixed-Methods Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods design that combines a systematic review of contemporaneous surveys and studies on fishermen's children with quantitative analysis of the 2020 National Population Census of Japan.

This study centres on children from fishing families who completed six years of elementary school but failed to complete three years of junior high school. Usui et al. (2024) identified non-completers of elementary education using the 2010 National Population Census, but could not identify junior high non-completers. In contrast, the 2020 National Population Census included this item, allowing more accurate identification of the level at which compulsory schooling was not completed.

[Insert Table 1 in this area.]

[Insert Table 2 in this area.]

[Insert Figure 1 in this area.]

Systematic Review Approach

The documents reviewed include surveys of junior-high long-term absence and studies on fishermen's children across Japan. These sources provide the basis for identifying prefectural patterns of child labour and trafficking.

Relevant literature (1945–2024) was collected through major English- and Japanese-language databases, including Google Scholar, J-STAGE, CiNii, and the National Diet Library, covering the whole of Japan. The review aimed to identify all available studies on fishermen’s children, long-term absence, and related labour practices in fishing villages. As part of the systematic review process, the comprehensive literature review by Eguchi (2022, Chapter 10, pp.483–504) was consulted as a secondary source summarising post-war scholarship on long-term absence and its institutional background, including studies related to evening junior high schools. Building on this review, the present study independently collected and examined additional historical and regional studies on child labour and locally specific labour practices in fishing communities that were not included in Eguchi’s survey.

Studies were classified into Group A, consisting of prefectures where absence was primarily linked to labour demands, and Group B, consisting of those where traditional trafficking practices were also documented. These materials form the empirical basis for the subsequent analysis.

Labour Demands in Fishing Villages

Studies of prefectures where child labour and long-term absence were reported

describe absence as structurally embedded in household labour regimes rather than individual attitudes. This background contrasts with prefectures where trafficking practices were also documented. This distinction underpins the classification presented in Table 1 and is contrasted with the mechanisms summarised in Table 2.

Traditional Child Trafficking Practices

In some prefectures, long-term absence was associated not only with household labour but also with traditional trafficking practices that placed children into indentured or foster labour. These practices, distinct from wage labour in fisheries, involved transferring children through contracts or advances, often formalised within community customs.

Examples include the *karego* system in Aomori and long-term indenture of children into fishing households in Okinawa, as summarised in Table 2.

Taken together, these practices show how structural child labour demands intersected with community-sanctioned systems of trafficking, intensifying constraints on compulsory education. This section complements the previous focus on labour demands alone and highlights the distinctive mechanisms identified in Group B prefectures.

Analytical Framework

This section outlines the analytical strategy used to examine whether prefectures historically affected by child labour and trafficking show higher proportions of junior high school non-completion. The analysis draws on the 2020 National Population Census and applies statistical tests of difference in population proportions (two-proportion z-tests, with corrections for multiple comparisons). This test assesses whether the proportion of non-completion in one prefecture is significantly higher than the national average. Corrections for multiple testing (false discovery rate, FDR) were applied to reduce the risk of spurious significance when comparing many prefectures simultaneously. The following subsections describe the census data, operationalisation of non-completion, and the aggregation of educational attainment among fishery workers.

Japanese National Population Census Data

The analysis draws on the 2020 National Population Census of Japan (MIC 2020), focusing on respondents aged 65–85 who were of compulsory school age during the 1950s–1970s. Educational attainment was reported as the highest level completed, which makes it possible to identify whether individuals finished elementary school, junior high school, or neither. Table 3 presents aggregated data on fishery workers in this cohort,

while Table 5 provides prefecture-level proportions used for statistical tests.

Non-Completion and Educational Attainment in the Census

This study distinguishes between long-term absence and non-completion: the former, defined in 1950s surveys of fishermen's children as ≥ 50 missed school days in a year, and the latter, represented by educational attainment categories in the 2020 National Population Census. The analysis tests whether prefectures with documented long-term absence exhibit higher rates of non-completion of junior high school.

[Insert Table 3 in this area.]

For clarity, this paper uses the modern term 'long-term absence'; the contemporaneous label 'long-term absenteeism' (*chōketsu*) is used only when quoting sources. Administrative and community reports also noted practices such as *jinshin baibai* ('human sale'), which encompassed exploitative fosterage or indenture. These categories reflect how mid-twentieth-century Japan classified educational disruption, distinct from modern statistical terminology.

In this study, non-completion of compulsory education is defined as: (a) not

enrolling in elementary or junior high school, or (b) dropping out of elementary or junior high school. These categories reflect how the census captures educational attainment. The cohort analysed here comprises individuals born between 1935 and 1955, whose junior high school years overlapped with, or followed shortly after, the period during which child labour and long-term absence were documented in the 1950s ⁽¹⁾. The design thus captures temporal overlap and proximity at the population level between historically documented educational disruption and later census-based educational outcomes, rather than exact contemporaneity or individual-level continuity.

Table 3 shows that non-completion of elementary school was rare among fishery workers (below 0.05% for both men and women), whereas non-completion of junior high school was around 0.7%—over ten times higher. These figures underline that long-term absence mainly translated into failure to complete junior high rather than elementary education. To ensure robustness when comparing multiple prefectures simultaneously, corrections for multiple testing were applied using the false discovery rate (FDR). After this adjustment, the main findings remained statistically significant, suggesting that they reflect genuine patterns rather than spurious results of multiple testing.

To clarify the temporal relationship between the analysed census cohorts and the surveys documenting long-term absence in the 1950s, Table 4 presents a heuristic

mapping of birth cohorts to their approximate junior high school attendance periods.

[Insert Table 4 in this area.]

Results

The hypothesis being tested is that areas with documented long-term absence are associated with higher rates of non-completion, as noted earlier. These areas are further divided into two groups: Group A refers to areas where child labour was investigated, corresponding to the light grey area in Figure 1 and related to Table 1, while Group B refers to areas where child labour was documented and, in addition, historical evidence of child trafficking was also reported, corresponding to the dark grey in Figure 1 and related to Table 2.

The null hypothesis (H_0) states no difference between prefectural and national proportions of non-completion. Hypothesis testing for the difference in population proportions is approximated by a normal distribution for each group, as the sample size was sufficiently large (see Table 5).

[Insert Table 5 in this area.]

Examining the overall trends, non-completion in Group A men (0.89%) and Group B women (1.53%) was significantly higher than the national proportion (0.70%) ($p < 0.01$ for men, $p < 0.001$ for women).

At the prefectural level, several areas with documented long-term absence showed significantly higher rates of non-completion of junior high school than the national average. In Group A, Hiroshima Prefecture stands out, with markedly elevated proportions of non-completion, particularly among men. As shown in Table 5, 24 out of 565 male fishery workers aged 65–85 in Hiroshima did not complete junior high school, corresponding to a proportion of 4.25%, which is more than six times the national average. Elevated non-completion was also observed among women in Hiroshima, where 6 out of 344 women (1.74%) did not complete junior high school, a proportion significantly higher than the national level. In addition to Hiroshima, several other prefectures listed in Table 5 exhibited significantly higher proportions than the national average. In Group B, elevated non-completion was observed among women in Okinawa, which is classified within Group B based on the historical documentation of child trafficking. As shown in Table 5, 3 out of 53 female fishery workers aged 65–85 in Okinawa did not complete junior high school, corresponding to a proportion of 5.66%, which is markedly higher

than the national average. A similarly elevated proportion was also observed among women in Aomori, where 14 out of 773 women (1.81%) did not complete junior high school. These prefectural-level differences also vary by gender, a pattern examined further in the Discussion. A sensitivity check regarding the inclusion of Okinawa is reported in Note (3).

Discussion

The purpose of this discussion is not to expand the analytical scope beyond the core question of educational non-completion, but to interpret the observed census patterns in light of historically documented labour-related absence.

The census indicators analysed here represent aggregated prefectural outcomes and are therefore interpreted as a population-level correspondence between historically documented labour practices and later educational non-completion, rather than as evidence of individual-level longitudinal causality. From this perspective, the findings suggest that compulsory education did not uniformly displace practices that removed children from schooling for labour, but rather that historically documented forms of educational disruption persisted at the regional level under heterogeneous institutional conditions.

Consistent with the patterns identified in Group A of the results, certain prefectures, notably Hiroshima, consistently exhibited high rates of junior high school non-completion, reflecting historically documented patterns of long-term absence associated with child labour under locally specific institutional conditions. In Hiroshima, many fishermen had been ‘put on the boat from a young age,’ and poor living conditions hindered sustained schooling attendance.

Beyond the Hiroshima case, archival surveys are complemented by a contemporary interview conducted in a fishing village in 2023 ⁽²⁾, which is consistent with the interpretation offered in this study that prolonged labour-related absence could be associated with non-completion of junior high school.

Results for Group B indicate relatively high rates of junior high school non-completion in Aomori and Okinawa, particularly among women. Interpreted in light of the literature summarised in Table 2, these patterns are compatible with historically documented labour practices and customary arrangements that constrained children’s sustained participation in schooling. In Aomori, existing studies report forms of child labour and indentured service embedded in local economic arrangements, including practices referred to as *karego*, in which children—especially girls—were incorporated into work under conditions that were difficult to reconcile with continuous school

attendance. Although the documentary record for Aomori is limited, these accounts provide a contextual basis for interpreting the elevated non-completion rates observed in the census as consistent with such practices. The documentary record is more extensive for Okinawa. As summarised in Table 2, the customary arrangement known as *itoman-ui* involved the placement of children into labour for Itoman fishing households from a young age, often under long-term commitments that effectively prioritised work over schooling. This arrangement shaped children's everyday lives and educational opportunities over extended periods. Within this context, the relatively high non-completion rates observed in Okinawa for both women and men can be interpreted as compatible with historically documented patterns of labour-related school absence.

These findings should be interpreted within a framework of conditional comparison rather than institutional equivalence. Although the analysis is conducted at the prefectural level, educational governance and labour practices in post-war Japan operated under heterogeneous institutional conditions. Okinawa is a particularly instructive case in this respect. Until 1972, it was administered under U.S. governance, and its educational system differed in important respects from those of mainland prefectures. The present study therefore does not assume uniform educational institutions across regions, nor does it attribute observed differences in non-completion rates to a

single policy regime. From this perspective, the persistence of elevated non-completion rates in Okinawa is not interpreted as direct evidence of national policy failure, but as an illustration of how labour-related educational disruption could manifest under distinct institutional conditions along a broader continuum of regional variation.

These institutional responses also have implications for adult lifelong learning. Without extending the analysis into adult education participation itself, this study aligns with perspectives that understand learning opportunities across the life course as embedded in layered institutional conditions (see Boeren, 2017). In this view, educational participation in adulthood is shaped not only by individual choice, but by cumulative institutional arrangements and constraints operating over time.

A limitation of this study lies in its treatment of gender disparities in school completion. Census data show that the proportion of women who did not complete junior high school was consistently higher than that of men, yet the underlying factors cannot be fully identified with the available evidence. Archival surveys provide some insight into gendered patterns of labour allocation: boys were more often mobilised fishing-related work and early occupational training, whereas girls were more commonly engaged in household support-related tasks (Mikami 1952; Saga 1952; Sato 1957; Kim 2003; Kato 2012; Sugimoto 2018). Taken together, these findings suggest that, under conditions of

economic necessity, the allocation of labour diverged by gender, reinforcing disparities in school non-completion.

This study provides empirical evidence that challenges implicit assumptions of uniform institutional effects often embedded in such theories. By demonstrating that labour-related educational exclusion persisted in certain regions despite the formal extension of compulsory education, the findings highlight the limits of interpreting educational expansion as a homogeneous or universally effective process.

Conclusion

This study has documented that prefectures with long-term absence in the 1950s also exhibit elevated rates of junior high school non-completion in the 2020 National Population Census, particularly in areas where child labour and traditional trafficking practices were prevalent. These findings are interpreted as indicating population-level correspondence between historically documented patterns of labour-related school absence and contemporary educational outcomes, without implying causal effects at the individual level. These findings contribute to understanding the enduring educational patterns associated with post-war child labour in fishing communities and clarify the value of integrating historical documentary evidence with census-based statistical

analysis. They also suggest that labour demands were gender-differentiated, with boys and girls mobilised into distinct roles that were associated with different schooling opportunities.

Situated within historically specific institutional contexts, the observed census-based patterns of school non-completion point to the relevance of life-course perspectives that emphasise the cumulative effects of educational disruption over time (Boeren, 2017). In this respect, relating historical labour practices to educational attainment aligns this study with international discussions that emphasise the importance of sustained investment in adult literacy and lifelong learning as components of inclusive and equitable education systems.

By complementing Japan-based educational historiography with population-level evidence, this study reframes historically documented educational exclusion as a structural and enduring feature of post-war institutional universality, rather than as a marginal or transitional anomaly.

Notes

(1) In this paper, the age of 85 is used as the cutoff point to distinguish between cohorts educated under the pre- and post-1947 compulsory education systems.

(2) On the morning of 10 October 2023, an interview was conducted with a social worker in a fishing village as part of a historical investigation into the relationship between child labour and long-term absence from elementary school in the district.

(3) Because Okinawa followed a distinct administrative trajectory under U.S. occupation until 1972, a sensitivity check was conducted to examine whether the inclusion of Okinawa affected the group-level comparisons reported in Table 5. In this supplementary analysis, Okinawa was excluded both from Group B and from the national reference population, and group-level proportions of junior high school non-completion were recalculated separately for men and women.

Among men, the proportion of non-completion in Group B excluding Okinawa (0.67%) was nearly identical to the national proportion excluding Okinawa (0.67%), and no statistically significant difference was observed ($p = 0.97$). Among women, the proportion in Group B excluding Okinawa (approximately 1.35%) remained higher than the corresponding national proportion excluding Okinawa (0.68%), and the difference remained statistically significant ($p = 0.01$).

Group A does not include Okinawa by definition; therefore, no corresponding sensitivity check was required for that group. These results indicate that the effect of excluding Okinawa is confined to Group B and differs by gender. The main conclusions reported in the text are

unchanged.

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Table 1. Summary of studies on long-term absence surveys (Group A) in Japanese fishing villages, 1950s.

Prefecture	Study	Contents
Hokkaido	Kagoyama (1955)	An interview survey examined fishing family work patterns and schooling, finding no significant stratified differences in long-term absence.
	Tomita (1951)	Seasonal squid fishing caused prolonged absences and undermined schooling.
Iwate	Saga (1952)	Absence patterns differed by labour system, with higher rates under individual collection.
Akita	Sato (1957)	In October, much of the village labour force worked in the Hachirō Lagoon fishery or in fish peddling, causing seasonal labour shortages in agriculture and marked long-term absences.
Ibaraki	Kimura (2015)	Teachers observed students working in fish processing during class hours, illustrating reliance on young labour.
Chiba	Tomita (1951)	Absence rates were higher in coastal towns, where early fishing was regarded as both training and preparation for working life.
	Mikami (1952)	Interviews indicated normative beliefs favouring early fishing work as training.
Kanagawa	Eguchi (2022)	In Yokohama, concerns over absence led to the establishment of evening classes.
Mie	Saga (1952)	A case study showed higher long-term absence in coastal fisheries than in pelagic fisheries.
Hyogo		

Eguchi (2022)

Post-war Iwaya Junior High faced long-term absences linked to fishing families, prompting the special and evening classes.

Hiroshima

Kim (2003)

On Yutakajima Island, children were often taken fishing from a young age, a practice that continued until the late 1950s, when poverty and fishing demands hindered school attendance and many children preferred fishing to inconsistent schooling.

Kagawa

Inai (1957)

In T City, fishing occupation was associated with non-enrolment, independent of family economic class.

Tokushima

Japan Teachers' Union (1953)

Tsuda Junior High created an evening class in 1952 for students with long-term absences, following an initiative by welfare commissioners, with students from all grades attending.

Ehime

Matsuno (1955)

In Miho Town, community-based junior high classes were established to accommodate long-term absentees from fishing families.

Note. Group A indicates prefectures where child labour was documented.

Table 2. Summary of studies on long-term absence surveys (Group B) in Japanese fishing villages involving child labour, including documented child trafficking, 1950s.

Prefecture	Study	Contents
Aomori	Toyoshima (2003)	The <i>karego</i> system employed children in fisheries and other labour, contributing to long-term absence.
Yamagata	Sugimoto (2018)	<i>Nankin kozō</i> indentured poor boys into fishing, depriving them of schooling.
Okayama	Women's & Minors Bureau of the Ministry of Labour (1953)	Government reports identified practices such as <i>Nankin kozō</i> , <i>kajiko</i> , and <i>funaban kozō</i> as child labour leading to loss of compulsory schooling.
Yamaguchi	Katoda (2009)	This paper examined the <i>kajiko</i> system on Nasake-jima Island, where child labour resulted in forced labour and educational exclusion.
Okinawa	Kato (2012)	The system of <i>itoman-ui</i> indentured children around age 10 to Itoman fishermen in exchange for a monetary advance, with contracts lasting until age 20; boys were employed in fishing, while girls worked as weavers, fish sellers, cooks, or babysitters.
	Skole (2015)	Female (b.1940): described her younger brother indentured at around age 10, forced into harsh swimming training and beaten if he failed. Male (b.1942): sold to Itoman at age 8, subjected to diving and heavy net hauling work; reflected that if he had continued junior high, his life would have been '180 degrees different'.
	Kato (2020)	A male born in 1939 recalled leaving junior high at 14 to apprentice under his father in chase-net fishing, working from 2 a.m. to 10 p.m. with no formal instruction.

Note. Group B indicates prefectures where child labour and trafficking were documented.

Table 3. Final educational attainment of fishery workers aged 65–85 in the 2020 Census, by sex.

	Elementary school	Junior high school		Elementary school	Junior high school
Men			Women		
Non-completion (<i>n</i> / <i>N</i>)	14 / 32688	230 / 32688	Non-completion (<i>n</i> / <i>N</i>)	4 / 12126	85 / 12126
Non-completion (%)	0.043%	0.704%	Non-completion (%)	0.033%	0.701%

Note. Data are from the 2020 National Census (MIC 2020). *N* = total number of fishery workers aged 65–85; *n* = number who did not complete the indicated level. The ratio *n* / *N* is reported both as a fraction and as a percentage.

Table 4. Heuristic Mapping of Birth Cohorts and Temporal Proximity to 1950s Surveys

Birth Cohort	Approximate Junior High School Attendance	Relationship to 1950s Surveys	Scholarly Interpretation
1935–1940	1947–1955	Direct overlap	Cohort contemporaneous with documented surveys
1941–1945	1953–1960	Partial overlap	Cohort overlapping with the later phase of surveys
1946–1950	1958–1965	Proximate	Cohort exposed during periods when documented practices were reported to persist
1951–1955	1963–1970	Late proximate	Subsequent cohort in which population-level effects may plausibly remain

Note. This table maps analysed birth cohorts to their approximate junior high school attendance periods in order to clarify temporal overlap and proximity to surveys documenting long-term absence and child labour practices in the 1950s. The mapping is intended to support methodological transparency and does not imply exact contemporaneity or causal continuity.

Table 5. Proportion of aged 65–85 Group Fishery Workers Who Did Not Complete Junior High School, by Prefecture (Data from the 2020 Census)

Prefectures	Men			Women		
	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>	%	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>	%
Total	32,688	230	0.704%	12,126	85	0.701%
Group A	14,100	126	0.894% **	6,445	50	0.776%
Hokkaido	5,174	26	0.503%	3,202	27	0.843%
Iwate	1,464	6	0.410%	455	3	0.659%
Akita	245	1	0.408%	51	1	1.961%
Ibaraki	338	4	1.183%	121	0	0.000%
Chiba	1,055	18	1.706% ***	308	1	0.325%
Kanagawa	310	4	1.290%	85	1	1.176%
Mie	1,234	3	0.243%	619	4	0.646%
Hyogo	1,039	22	2.117% ***	242	2	0.826%
Hiroshima	565	24	4.248% ***	344	6	1.744% *
Tokushima	624	1	0.160%	202	2	0.990%
Kagawa	422	9	2.133% ***	133	0	0.000%
Ehime	1,141	7	0.613%	508	3	0.591%
Group B	3,828	36	0.940% ***	1,239	19	1.533% ***
Aomori	1,718	18	1.048% ***	773	14	1.811% ***
Yamagata	186	0	0.000%	44	0	0.000%
Okayama	213	2	0.939%	90	0	0.000%
Yamaguchi	1,182	2	0.169% *	279	2	0.717%
Okinawa	529	14	2.647% ***	53	3	5.660% ***
Other	14,760	68	0.461% ***	4,442	16	0.360% ***
Fukushima	277	3	1.083%	104	1	0.962%
Tochigi	25	0	0.000%	21	0	0.000%
Gunma	22	0	0.000%	9	0	0.000%
Saitama	23	0	0.000%	16	0	0.000%
Tokyo	160	0	0.000%	19	0	0.000%
Niigata	489	1	0.204%	175	0	0.000%
Toyama	173	0	0.000%	43	0	0.000%
Ishikawa	531	2	0.377%	160	3	1.875%
Fukui	277	2	0.722%	50	0	0.000%
Yamanashi	23	0	0.000%	10	0	0.000%
Nagano	44	0	0.000%	28	0	0.000%
Gifu	50	0	0.000%	24	0	0.000%
Shizuoka	941	0	0.000%	200	0	0.000%
Aichi	712	0	0.000%	294	1	0.340%
Shiga	133	0	0.000%	63	0	0.000%
Kyoto	190	0	0.000%	43	0	0.000%
Osaka	137	3	2.190% *	43	3	6.977% ***
Nara	16	0	0.000%	10	0	0.000%
Wakayama	534	12	2.247% ***	98	0	0.000%
Tottori	227	1	0.441%	35	0	0.000%
Shimane	773	0	0.000%	164	1	0.610%
Kochi	868	5	0.576%	156	0	0.000%

Fukuoka	752	5	0.665%	293	0	0.000%
Saga	559	2	0.358%	280	0	0.000%
Nagasaki	2,459	12	0.488%	710	2	0.282%
Kumamoto	970	7	0.722%	402	3	0.746%
Oita	841	3	0.357%	256	0	0.000%
Miyazaki	525	4	0.762%	146	0	0.000%
Kagoshima	974	4	0.411%	250	2	0.800%

Note. Data are from the 2020 National Census (MIC 2020). Population: fishery workers aged 65–85. Percentages (%) indicate the proportion who did not complete junior high school. N denotes the total population and n denotes the number of non-completers; the ratio n / N is reported both as a fraction and as a percentage. All prefectures are listed. Group A indicates prefectures where long-term absence due to child labour was documented (Table 1). Group B indicates prefectures where, in addition to child labour, child trafficking was also documented (Table 2). Other comprises all remaining prefectures.

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. Table 4 reports proportions as percentages (%), whereas Supplementary Table S1 reports the same ratios (n / N) in decimal form as Prop.

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of Japanese prefectures where child labour was reported in the 1950s, including cases involving child trafficking.

Note. Light grey = Group A (Child labour). Dark grey = Group B (Child labour and trafficking). White = Prefectures with no available studies.